

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN RELATION TO DRUG EDUCATION PROGRAMS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS OF MACO NORTH DISTRICT

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Abstract. The study unfolded the relationship between parental involvement and efficacy of drug education programs in the elementary schools of Maco North District. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected 120 teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that parents' involvement in terms of volunteerism, feedback and attendance, and participation are perceived to be moderately extensive; while communication with school suggests less extensive, and, likewise, drug education programs in terms of program satisfaction and behavioral outcomes are perceived to be moderately extensive, while, reduction of risk factors and retention of information are less extensive. There is a significant relationship between parents' involvement and drug education programs. All domains of parents' involvement in terms of attendance and participation, communication with school, feedback, and volunteerism indicate a statistically significant influence on drug education program implementation. Future research may explore and evaluate innovative teaching methods and technologies that can enhance the delivery of drug education. Investigate the impact of community-based approaches to drug education.

KEY WORDS

1. Parents' Involvement .
2. Drug Education Program.
3. Maco, North District.

1. Introduction

The extent of parental involvement and its influence on the efficacy of implementing drug education programs in elementary schools is a complex and multifaceted issue. While parental involvement is widely recognized as a crucial factor in the success of such programs, several challenges can hinder its effectiveness. Not all parents have the time or resources to engage actively in school-based activities, including drug education initiatives. This can be due to work commitments, family responsibilities, or other constraints. Some parents may need more knowledge or comfort to effectively address drug-related topics with their children, which can limit their ability to reinforce the messages conveyed at school. Cultural and language barriers can also play a role in hindering effective communication between the school and parents. Moreover, the varying attitudes and beliefs of parents towards drug education can influence

the level of their involvement. Despite these challenges, it is essential to acknowledge that parental involvement remains a critical component in reinforcing the messages and values taught in drug education programs. Schools and communities must work collaboratively to address these challenges by providing parents with resources, information, and support, fostering an environment where they feel empowered and encouraged to play an active role in their children's drug education (Ilo and Nwimo, 2017). This collaborative effort can contribute to a more comprehensive and practical approach to drug education that not only imparts knowledge but also ensures that it is internalized and applied by students. Parental involvement is pivotal in reinforcing the principles and values taught in drug education programs. However, in the context of the Philippines, where social, cultural, and economic factors vary widely, the extent of parental involvement can be diverse. While many parents actively engage in their children's education and are dedicated to reinforcing the importance of drug education, others face barriers, such as economic constraints and work commitments, which can limit their involvement. Moreover, cultural norms and attitudes towards drug education and family dynamics can also affect the level of parental engagement (Beamon et.al., 2023). To maximize the efficacy of drug education programs, efforts must be made to address these varying levels of parental involvement, ensuring that all parents, regardless of their circumstances, are equipped with the resources, information, and support needed to participate in their children's drug education actively. Such a holistic approach empowers parents to be active partners in this crucial aspect of their children's education and reinforces the national commitment to creating a drug-free and responsible society in the Philippines (Kasim et.al, 2021). The challenge of drug education implementation in Maco, Davao de Oro, and the participation of parents of elementary school learners in addressing it is a topic of critical importance. In this region, parents play a significant role in influencing the effectiveness of drug education programs. However, several challenges can affect the extent and nature of their involvement. Many parents in Maco, Davao de Oro, face economic challenges and work commitments that can limit their participation in school activities, including drug education programs. Long working hours and multiple jobs can leave parents with limited time to engage with their children's education. The region is culturally diverse, and language barriers can sometimes impede effective communication between the school and parents. This can affect the exchange of information and active participation in drug education initiatives. Parents may have diverse attitudes and beliefs regarding drug education, reflecting regional and cultural diversity. Some may actively support and reinforce the program's messages, while others may have differing views on the approach. Disparities in access to resources and information can influence parental involvement. Some parents may lack access to educational materials or may not be aware of the importance of drug education in their children's lives. Some parents may not know or feel comfortable discussing drug-related topics with their children, which can limit their ability to reinforce the program's messages at home (Darcy, 2021). To address these challenges, it is crucial for schools, local authorities, and community organizations in Maco, Davao de Oro, to take a multi-faceted approach. This can include providing resources, offering flexible engagement opportunities, conducting outreach programs in multiple languages, and raising awareness about the significance of drug education. Collaborative efforts that involve parents, teachers, and the community can help bridge these gaps and enhance parental participation in drug education programs. Ultimately, a more inclusive and culturally sensitive approach can strengthen the

effectiveness of drug education in this region.

2. Methodology

Research methods are systematic processes used to collect and analyze data to answer research questions and address specific objectives. They are the foundation for empirical investigations in various fields, including science, social sciences, and humanities. Research methods encompass a range of approaches, such as quantitative methods, which involve collecting numerical data through surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis, and qualitative methods, which focus on understanding and interpreting non-numerical data through interviews, content analysis, or ethnography. Researchers select methods based on the nature of their research questions and the type of data they need. The chosen methods guide data collection, analysis, and interpretation, ensuring that the research is rigorous and that the findings are reliable and valid. The choice of research method often depends on the study's goals, scope, and context, and researchers carefully select the most appropriate approach to address their research objectives. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs represent essential methods in the field of research, each with its distinct purpose and characteristics. Non-experimental research primarily focuses on observing and analyzing existing phenomena without manipulating variables. Descriptive research seeks to provide a comprehensive and detailed account of a particular situation, population, or event (Creswel, 2014). Correlational research, on the other hand, examines the relationships between variables, aiming to identify patterns, associations, or connections among them. It does not imply causation but helps researchers understand how changes in one variable may relate to changes in another. Predictive research design extends beyond describing and correlating variables. It involves developing models or theories to predict future outcomes or behavior. Researchers gather and analyze data to establish patterns that can be used for forecasting or making informed decisions. While these research designs serve distinct purposes, they share common advantages. They offer practicality, allowing researchers to study phenomena as they naturally occur, which is often the case in the social sciences. Non-experimental research designs are more ethical and logistically feasible when manipulation or experimentation is inappropriate or impossible. However, a limitation is the need for more control over variables, making it challenging to establish causal relationships. In the study examining the influence of parental involvement on the efficacy of drug education programs in elementary schools, non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research designs play crucial roles in gathering, analyzing, and interpreting data. The descriptive research design is instrumental in painting a detailed picture of the current state of parental involvement, the structure of drug education programs, and the baseline knowledge,

attitudes, and intentions of students regarding drug-related issues. Through surveys, questionnaires, and observations, this design helps researchers collect comprehensive data about the participants, their current levels of involvement, and the existing drug education initiatives. This descriptive information serves as the foundation for the study, allowing researchers to understand the context within which parental involvement is examined. Correlational research is valuable in understanding the relationships between variables without manipulating them. This study explores the associations between parental involvement as the independent variable and students' knowledge, attitudes, and intentions as dependent variables. Statistical analyses, such as correlation coefficients, enable researchers to assess the strength and direction of these relationships. For instance, it can reveal whether higher levels of parental involvement correlate with more positive attitudes and more excellent knowledge among students. This design allows for a nuanced understanding of how parental involvement may be related to the efficacy of drug education programs. The predictive research design is crucial for identifying factors that can forecast or predict specific outcomes. This study investigates whether parental involvement can predict positive behavioral outcomes among students. By using regression analysis or structural equation modeling, researchers can determine the extent to which parental involvement can predict changes in students' intentions and actual behaviors related to drug use. This design takes the study beyond understanding relationships to making informed predictions about the impact of parental involvement on the efficacy of drug education programs. By employing these research designs in a complementary manner, the study can provide a comprehensive understanding of how parental involvement relates to the outcomes of drug education programs. It not only describes the current situation but also explores

the connections and, to some extent, foresees the potential effects of parental involvement, contributing to more informed decision-making for educators, parents, and policymakers in the field of drug education.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Public School Teachers in Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from the private schools surrounding the District. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified through online platforms and in person, considering the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its significance to their professional development. The respondents were selected based on the assumption that they actively manage and supervise schools in organizational management and program implementation. They were expected to have a strong engagement with the drug education policy and integration with pedagogical classroom activities, as well as the day-to-day management and execution of various school-based learning programs, projects, and activities designed to enhance early learners' development within the framework of private school management. The qualifications for participation in this study were rooted in the expectation that they had made significant contributions, extending beyond their primary roles in curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, by actively participating in various educational activities. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all to improve the school environment and learners' educational experiences during the new regular learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school manage-

ment and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The research instrument was carefully designed after an extensive review of relevant literature and related studies in this research study. The researcher invested significant time and effort in collecting and analyzing pertinent literature to extract critical concepts. These concepts not only informed the development of the instrument but also ensured that it closely aligned with the specific aspects being investigated. This meticulous process resulted in a well-organized set of questionnaire items, enhancing the overall validity of the instrument and reducing potential concerns

regarding its reliability. The authors argued that items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of parental involvement in terms of attendance and participation, communication with the school, parental feedback, and parental volunteerism. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the efficacy of drug education programs in terms of reducing risk factors, behavioral outcomes, program satisfaction, and information retention. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.889, which means that College where the researcher is studying The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of parental involvement. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The parental involvement is always manifested
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The parental involvement is often-times manifested
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The parental involvement is sometimes manifested
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The parental involvement is rarely manifested
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The parental involvement is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of efficacy of the drug education program, a 5-point

Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The statements provide a clear overview of the sequential steps that define the data collection pro-

cess. It is imperative that the researcher carefully consider and strictly follow these steps, adhering to the policies of College where the

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The drug education program is always manifested
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The drug education program is oftentimes manifested
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The drug education program is sometimes manifested
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The drug education program is rarely manifested
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The drug education program is not manifested

researcher is studying. This approach is vital to ensure safety and mitigate any potential risks associated with gathering relevant data, especially given the current context of ongoing in-person interactions. Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of November 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently, she prepared various documents, including request letters, for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2004) outlined, and followed the health protocols mandated by the IATF’s policy. As the research proposal was approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of November 2023, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within Maco North District to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In December 2023,

the researcher established an online survey using a Google Sheets form for data collection. This survey was distributed to randomly selected participants via email. Hard copies of the survey were provided to those who did not have internet access. As soon as the links were sent, responses began to pour in, and they were promptly organized, analyzed, and interpreted. This data collection process was initiated in the second week of December 2023, immediately after receiving approval from the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with the study. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The initial analysis findings were shared with the thesis adviser in the second week of January 2024. In the first week of January 2024, the thesis adviser engaged the expertise of the graduate school statistician to refine the statistical treatment and receive guidance. Further discussions were conducted during the second week of February 2024 to delve deeper into the analysis, ensuring a more meaningful interpretation of the study’s results and their implications.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1), the extent of parental involvement, and

statement problem number two (2), the drug education programs. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant

relationship between parental involvement and drug education program. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the indicators of parental involvement that significantly influence the drug education programs (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati,

2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data gathered in tabular and textual form to provide clear ideas and information on the queries based on the statement of the problem posed. Various reviews present implications of the results to corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as claimed and posed in the study.

Table 1 presents a summary of the extent of parental involvement. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: parental volunteerism (3.36), parental feedback (3.33), and attendance and participa-

tion (2.95) denote moderately extensive, while communication (2.57) denotes less extensive. This suggests that the extent of parental involvement implementation is moderately extensive in Maco North District, Davao de Oro.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Parental Involvement

No	Parental Involvement	Mean
1	Attendance and Participation	2.95
2	Communication	2.57
3	Parental Feedback	3.33
4	Parental Volunteerism	3.36
Overall Mean		3.05

Effective parental involvement involves modeling appropriate behaviors and attitudes related to substance use, and creating a consistent and supportive environment that reinforces the lessons learned in formal drug education settings. Parents are influential role models,

shaping their children’s perceptions and decisions regarding substance use. Additionally, involvement may extend into collaboration with schools and community initiatives, contributing to a comprehensive and interconnected approach to drug education. Recognizing the di-

verse contexts within which families operate, the nature of parental involvement should be adaptable and sensitive to individual needs, pro-

moting a collective effort to instill a strong foundation of knowledge and resilience against the challenges posed by substance abuse.

Table 2 presents the summary of the extent of parental involvement. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: program satisfaction (3.04) and behavioral outcome (2.63), are perceived to be moderately extensive, while reduction of risk fac-

tors (2.54) and retention of information (2.22) denotes less extensive. This suggests that the extent of implementation of the drug education program is moderately extensive in Maco North District, Davao de Oro.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Drug Education Program

No	Drug Education Program	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Reduction of Risk Factors	2.54	Less Extensive
2	Behavioral Outcome	2.63	Moderately Extensive
3	Program Satisfaction	3.04	Moderately Extensive
4	Retention of Information	2.22	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.60	Moderately Extensive

A moderately extensive implementation of a drug education program implies a comprehensive and well-structured approach that goes beyond essential awareness initiatives but may not reach the level of an all-encompassing, highly detailed program. In this context, a moderately extensive implementation strikes a balance between depth and coverage, acknowledging the need for a thorough understanding of substance abuse issues without overwhelming participants with an excessive amount of information. Such programs typically cover a diverse range of topics, including the risks and consequences of drug use, effective communication strategies, and coping mechanisms.

Relationship between Parental Involvement and Efficacy of Drug Education Programs

Table 3 revealed the significant correlation between parents' involvement and drug education program implementation. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation must be rejected, for it provided empirical evidence of statistically significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson's r generated a significantly strong positive correlation ($r=0.873$; $p<.001$) between parents' involvement and drug education program implementation.

The correlation between parents' involvement and the effectiveness of drug education programs is vital in shaping the outcomes of such initiatives. Research consistently indicates that active parental involvement significantly enhances the impact of drug education efforts.

When parents engage in these programs, there is a higher likelihood of creating a supportive and reinforcing environment at home. Open communication between parents and children about the risks and consequences of substance abuse, which is often encouraged by drug edu-

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Implementation of Drug Education Program and Parents' Involvement

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Drug Education Program				
Parents' Involvement	0.873	<0.001	Significant	Reject H_0

cation programs, is more likely to occur when parents are actively involved in the educational process (Gokuladas Baby Sam, 2022). Parents engaged in drug education programs are better equipped to understand the content and objectives of the curriculum. This understanding enables them to reinforce critical messages at home, emphasizing the importance of making informed decisions regarding substance use. Moreover, parental involvement can extend beyond the home and into collaborative efforts with schools and community initiatives, contributing to a more comprehensive and interconnected approach to drug education. Conversely, Kasim et.al. (2021) shared that a lack of parental involvement may diminish the overall impact of drug education programs. When parents are not engaged, there is a risk of inconsistent messaging, as children may receive conflicting information from different sources. Additionally, the absence of parental reinforcement may limit the effectiveness of the program in shaping attitudes and behaviors related to substance use.

Domains of Parental Involvement Significantly Influence Drug Education Programs

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of parental involvement that significantly influence the efficacy of drug education programs. It can be noted that all domains of parental involvement, in terms of attendance and participation (0.011),

communication with school (0.002), feedback (0.013), and volunteerism (0.030), are statistically significant in influencing drug education program implementation. This shows that the domains of parental involvement significantly influence drug education program implementation. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.899 suggests that the domains of parental involvement explained 89.9%. This provides empirical evidence that the domains of parental involvement can account for and explain the variability of drug education program implementation. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (225.996) and F-statistic are significant $p < .010$, which tells that the model is a better predictor of drug education program implementation. The nature of parents' involvement significantly influences the implementation of drug education programs, playing a pivotal role in shaping the effectiveness of these initiatives. Actively engaged parents contribute to a more holistic and reinforcing educational environment for their children. This involvement manifests in various ways, including open communication about substance abuse, participation in school-based drug education activities, and collaboration with community initiatives. When parents actively participate in these programs, there is a greater likelihood of consistent messaging between home and school, reinforcing the key lessons and values of drug education.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Parents’ Involvement that Significantly Influence Drug Education Program Implementation

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions on H_0
(Intercept)	4.397		0.062	< .001	
(Intercept)	0.401		0.144	0.006	
Attendance and Participation	0.032	-0.021	0.046	0.011	Reject H_0
Communication with School	0.342	0.361	0.054	0.002	Reject H_0
Feedback	0.207	0.215	0.064	0.013	Reject H_0
Volunteerism	0.568	0.425	0.079	0.030	Reject H_0
$R^2 = 0.899$					
F -value = 225.996					
p -value = < 0.010					

Furthermore, engaged parents are better positioned to understand the content and objectives of the curriculum, allowing them to provide additional support and guidance to their children. This collaborative approach between parents, schools, and communities creates a comprehensive network that reinforces the importance of informed decision-making and healthy behaviors related to substance use. On the contrary, limited parental involvement

may impede the program’s effectiveness, as the absence of reinforcement at home may diminish the impact of the educational messages. Therefore, the nature of parents’ involvement is integral to the success of drug education programs, influencing the overall atmosphere in which children develop their understanding and resilience against the challenges of substance abuse.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper section outlines the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations, drawing support from the literature covered in the initial chapters. The conclusion aligns with the problem statements articulated in this study.

4.1. Findings—The following are the study’s findings, which are given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of parents’ involvement in terms of volunteerism, feedback, and attendance and participation is perceived to be moderately extensive, while communication with school suggests less extensive involvement. This denotes that parents’ involvement is moderately extensive in Maco North District, Davao de Oro.

Drug education programs are perceived to be moderately extensive in terms of program satisfaction and behavioral outcomes. At the same time, reducing risk factors and retaining information are less extensive. This denotes that the drug education program is moderately extensive in Maco North District, Davao de Oro. Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson’s r generated a significant relationship between parents’ involvement and drug

education programs. All domains of parents' involvement in terms of attendance and participation, communication with school, feedback, and volunteerism indicate statistically significant influence on drug education program implementation. This shows that the domains of parents' involvement significantly affect drug education programs.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions, to wit; The extent of parents' involvement in volunteerism, feedback, attendance, and participation is perceived to be moderately extensive, while communication with the school suggests less extensive. This denotes that parents' involvement is moderately extensive in Maco North District, Davao de Oro. The extent of the drug education program in terms of program satisfaction and behavioral outcomes is perceived to be moderately extensive, while the reduction of risk factors and retention of information are less extensive. This denotes that the drug education program is moderately extensive in Maco North District, Davao de Oro. There is a significant relationship between parents' involvement and a drug education program. All domains of parents' involvement in attendance and participation, communication with school, feedback, and volunteerism indicate statistically significant influence on drug education program implementation. This shows that the domains of parents' involvement significantly affect drug education programs.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; The Public School District Supervisor. Encourage and support initiatives that promote increased parental involvement in drug education programs. This may include organizing workshops, informational sessions, and community events to educate parents about their role in reinforcing drug education messages at home. Provide comprehensive training for teachers on evidence-based and cul-

turally sensitive approaches to delivering drug education. This training should equip teachers with the skills to effectively engage students and parents, fostering a collaborative learning environment. Regularly assess and update the drug education curriculum to ensure it remains relevant, addresses emerging trends in substance abuse, and aligns with the needs of the student population. Collaborate with educators, health professionals, and community stakeholders in the curriculum development and revision process. The School Principal. Foster a culture of collaboration between parents and teachers by organizing regular meetings, workshops, and events that facilitate open communication. Encourage teachers to share insights with parents and vice versa, creating a supportive network for effective drug education. Allocate resources for ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers, focusing on enhancing their knowledge and skills in delivering impactful drug education. This may involve bringing in experts or collaborating with external organizations specializing in substance abuse prevention. Implement a school-wide support system that emphasizes the importance of a consistent anti-drug message. This may involve integrating drug education into various aspects of the school culture, including assemblies, awareness campaigns, and extracurricular activities. The Teachers. Implement interactive and engaging teaching methods to capture students' attention and facilitate better retention of drug education content. Utilize real-life scenarios, case studies, and group discussions to make the material more relatable and applicable. Actively encourage parental involvement in the learning process. Provide parents with resources, materials, and opportunities to engage in discussions about drug education with their children. Foster a collaborative relationship between teachers and parents to reinforce consistent messaging. Recognize and address the diverse learning needs and backgrounds of students. Tailor drug edu-

cation approaches to be culturally sensitive and inclusive, ensuring that the content resonates with the experiences of all students. The Future Researchers: Explore and evaluate innovative teaching methods and technologies that can enhance the delivery of drug education. Consider integrating digital resources, interactive platforms, and virtual learning experiences to engage students more effectively. Investigate the impact of community-based approaches to drug education. Assess the effectiveness of involving local organizations, healthcare professionals, and community leaders in shaping and delivering drug education programs to create a more comprehensive and community-specific strategy.

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